

Stilbenoids and sesquiterpene derivatives of the orchids *Gastrochilum calcoelaria* and *Dendrobium amoenum* : Application of 2D NMR spectroscopy in structural elucidation of complex natural products[†]

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Abstract : Systematic chemical investigation of the Indian orchid *Gastrochilum calcoelaria* D. Don for the first time afforded two new bibenzyl derivatives, designated gastrochilin and gastrochilinin, besides the compounds confusarin [2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,8-trimethoxyphenanthrene] and 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene. The orchid *Dendrobium amoenum* Wall was chemically investigated earlier. Further chemical investigation of this Indian orchid has resulted in the isolation of yet another new bibenzyl derivative amoenylinin, besides the previously reported stilbenoids amoenylin [4-hydroxy-3,4',5-trimethoxybibenzyl], isoamoenylin [3'-hydroxy-3,4,5-trimethoxybibenzyl], moscatilin [4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3',5-trimethoxybibenzyl], batatasin-III [3,3'-dihydroxy-5-methoxybibenzyl], 3,4'-dihydroxy-5-methoxybibenzyl, the two phenanthrenes confusarin and 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene, the two phenanthropyran derivatives imbricatin [2,7-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-9,10-dihydro-5H-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran] and flaccidin [2,6-dihydroxy-7-methoxy-9,10-dihydro-5H-phenanthro[4,5-*bcd*]pyran], the two sesquiterpenoids amotin and amoenin, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and β -sitosterol. The structures of gastrochilin, gastrochilinin and amoenylinin are established as 2'-hydroxy-3,3'-dimethoxy-4,5-methylenedioxybibenzyl, 2',3,3'-trimethoxy-4,5-methylenedioxybibenzyl and 3,3',4,4',5-pentamethoxybibenzyl, respectively, from spectral and chemical evidence. Additional spectral evidence for 3,4'-dihydroxy-5-methoxybibenzyl and detailed 2D NMR spectral analysis of amotin are provided for further confirmation of their assigned structures.

Keywords : *Gastrochilum calcoelaria* D. Don, *Dendrobium amoenum* Wall, Orchidaceae, gastrochilin, gastrochilinin, amoenylinin, 3,4'-dihydroxy-5-methoxybibenzyl, bibenzyl derivatives, 2D NMR spectral analysis of amotin, amoenin, sesquiterpene derivatives.

Introduction

We reported earlier the isolation of a fairly large number of phytochemicals from a series of Indian orchids. These compounds encompass a wide variety of stilbenoids, viz. stilbene¹, bibenzyls², phenanthrenes and 9,10-dihydrophenanthrenes^{3,4} and their dimers⁵⁻¹⁰, phenanthropyrans and pyrones and their 9,10-dihydro derivatives¹¹⁻¹⁷, fluorenones¹⁸ and a few other polyphenolics^{19,20}, several triterpenoids²¹⁻²³, steroids of biogenetic importance²⁴⁻²⁶ and some simple aromatic compounds²⁷. As part of this general programme of research, we chemically investigated the orchid *Gastrochilum calcoelaria* which resulted in the isolation of two new bibenzyl derivatives, designated gastrochilin and gastrochilinin, in

addition to the phenanthrene derivatives confusarin²⁸ (1a) and 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene²⁹ (1b). We have also reinvestigated the orchid *Dendrobium amoenum*. This has afforded yet another new bibenzyl derivative amoenylinin, besides *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, β -sitosterol, the known bibenzyl derivatives amoenylin² (2a) and isoamoenylin² (2b) [isolated by us earlier from the same orchid], moscatilin³⁰ (2c), batatasin-III³¹ (2d) and 3,4'-dihydroxy-5-methoxybibenzyl³² (2e), the two 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyrans imbricatin³³ (3a) and flaccidin³⁴ (3b), the phenanthrenes 1a and 1b, in addition to the sesquiterpenoids amotin³⁵ (4) and amoenin³⁶ (5). The structures of gastrochilin, gastrochilinin and amoenylinin were established as 2'-hydroxy-3,3'-

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

dimethoxy-4,5-methylenedioxybibenzyl (**2f**), 2',3,3'-trimethoxy-4,5-methylenedioxybibenzyl (**2g**) and 3,3',4,4',5-pentamethoxybibenzyl (**2h**), respectively, from spectral and chemical evidence. In this paper, we also present additional spectral data of **2e**, and a detailed 2D NMR spectral (COSY, HMQC and HMBC) analysis of amotin (**4**) for further confirmation of their assigned structures.

Results and discussion

Gastrochilin (**2f**), $C_{17}H_{18}O_5$ (M^+ at m/z 302), gastrochilinin (**2g**), $C_{18}H_{20}O_5$ (M^+ at m/z 316) and amoeylinin (**2h**), $C_{19}H_{24}O_5$ (M^+ at m/z 332), all showed typical benzenoid UV absorptions² [**2f**: λ_{\max} 211.5 and 277.5 nm (log ϵ 4.21 and 3.06); **2g**: λ_{\max} 221.0 and 276.5 nm (log ϵ 4.16 and 3.36); **2h**: λ_{\max} 210.5 and 277.5 nm (log ϵ 4.23 and 3.20)]. This would suggest the presence of the bibenzyl chromophoric system in all the three compounds. **2f** is phenolic in nature as evident from its characteristic colour reactions, solubility in NaOH, alkali-induced bathochromic shifts of its UV maxima and by its IR spectrum showing characteristic band at ν_{\max} 3400 cm^{-1} . The presence of one phenolic hydroxyl group in **2f** was confirmed by the formation of an acetyl derivative (**2i**), $C_{19}H_{20}O_6$ (M^+ at m/z 344) with Ac_2O and pyridine. The IR spectrum of **2i**, as expected, lacked the band for hydroxyl group of **2f** and, instead, showed bands at ν_{\max} 1250 and 1750 cm^{-1} for an acetoxy function.

Gastrochilinin (**2g**) and amoeylinin (**2h**), on the other hand, are devoid of any phenolic hydroxyl group as evident from their insolubility in NaOH solution and their IR spectra exhibiting the absence of any hydroxyl absorption band.

The 1H NMR spectrum of each of **2f**, **2g** and **2h** is characterized by the presence of a four-proton signal in the region of δ 2.75–2.85 [**2f**: δ 2.88 (m); **2g**: δ 2.80 and 2.88 (each 2H, m); **2h**: δ 2.83 (s)] which is typical of a bibenzyl derivative² indicating the bibenzyl skeletal structure of all the three compounds. The presence of a single phenolic hydroxyl function in **2f** was indicated by the signal at δ 5.70 (1H, s; disappeared on deuterium exchange) in the 1H NMR spectrum of the compound. This was also supported by the fact that the above signal was replaced by the signal at δ 2.35 (3H, s) in the 1H NMR spectrum of gastrochilin acetate (**2i**), which corresponded to an acetate methyl. The absence of any such exchangeable proton signal in the spectra of **2g** and **2h**, on the other hand, affirmed the neutral character of both

the compounds. The 1H NMR spectra of both **2f** and **2g** showed the presence of a methylenedioxy function [**2f**: δ 5.92 (2H, s); **2g**: δ 5.93 (2H, s)]. While the spectrum of **2f** exhibited signals for two aromatic methoxyl groups [δ 3.86 and 3.89 (each 3H, s)], that of **2g** showed three such functional groups [δ 3.81 (3H, s) and 3.86 (6H, s)]. The 1H NMR spectrum of **2h**, on the other hand, is devoid of any signal for a methylenedioxy function and, instead, showed the signals for five aromatic methoxyl groups [δ 3.82 (9H, s) and 3.84 and 3.86 (each 3H, s)]. Thus, the five oxygen atoms of **2f**, **2g** and **2h** are accounted for in each of these compounds in terms of the oxygenated functional groups indicated above. The 1H NMR spectra of all the three compounds also showed signals for five aromatic protons [**2f**: δ 6.35 (1H, d, $J=1.15$ Hz), 6.44 (1H, d, $J=1.15$ Hz), 6.74 (1H, ill-res., appt. t) and 6.71–6.77 (2H, m); **2g**: δ 6.33 and 6.42 (each 1H, br. s), 6.74 (1H, d, $J=7.58$ Hz), 6.79 (1H, d, $J=7.88$ Hz) and 6.97 (1H, appt. t, $J_1=7.88$ Hz and $J_2=7.58$ Hz); **2h**: δ 6.37 (2H, s), 6.66 (1H, d, $J=1.86$ Hz), 6.72 (1H, dd, $J_1=8.1$ Hz and $J_2=1.86$ Hz) and 6.79 (1H, d, $J=8.1$ Hz)].

The most convincing evidence for the bibenzyl formulation for all the three compounds **2f**, **2g** and **2h** and the distribution of the functional groups in the two phenyl rings A and B in each of these compounds were provided by the mass spectral fragmentations of the compounds. The major fragmentation of these compounds involves the facile cleavage of the doubly benzylic $C_{\alpha}-C_{\alpha'}$ bond leading to two resonance-stabilized benzylic ion-fragments which are diagnostic of their bibenzyl formulation. The m/z values of these ion-fragments indicate the nature and the number of the substituents in the two phenyl rings A and B of each of these compounds, the relative positions of these functional groups in each compound being ascertained by the chemical shifts and the splitting patterns of the aromatic protons of the compounds. Thus, the mass spectrum of each of **2f**, **2g** and **2h** showed a pair of intense peaks corresponding to the two highly stabilized benzylic ion-fragments formed by the cleavage of the doubly benzylic $C_{\alpha}-C_{\alpha'}$ bond [**2f**: ion-fragments a (m/z 165) and b (m/z 137); **2g**: a (m/z 165) and c (m/z 151); **2h**: d (m/z 181) and e (m/z 151; isomeric with c)] (Scheme 1). The appearance of the same intense peak at m/z 165 (ion-fragment a) in the mass spectra of both gastrochilin (**2f**) and gastrochilinin (**2g**) corresponding to their phenyl ring A suggests that their ring A contains the same functional groups, viz. a methoxy and a methylenedioxy group. That the above functional groups are located at C-3 and C-4,

1a : R¹ = H, R² = OMe

1b : R¹ = OMe, R² = H

3a : R¹ = H, R² = Me

3b : R¹ = Me, R² = H

2a : R¹ = R² = R³ = OMe, R⁴ = OH, R⁵ = R⁶ = R⁷ = H

2b : R¹ = R² = R³ = OMe, R⁴ = R⁵ = R⁶ = H, R⁷ = OH

2c : R¹ = R² = R³ = OMe, R⁴ = R⁵ = OH, R⁶ = R⁷ = H

2d : R¹ = R⁵ = OH, R² = R⁴ = R⁶ = R⁷ = H, R³ = OMe

2e : R¹ = R⁶ = OH, R² = R⁴ = R⁵ = R⁷ = H, R³ = OMe

2f : R¹ = R⁵ = OMe, R², R³ = -OCH₂O-, R⁴ = OH, R⁶ = R⁷ = H

2g : R¹ = R⁴ = R⁶ = OMe, R², R³ = -OCH₂O-, R⁵ = R⁷ = H

2h : R¹ = R² = R³ = R⁴ = OMe, R⁵ = R⁷ = H

2i : R¹ = R⁶ = OMe, R², R³ = -OCH₂O-, R⁴ = OAc, R⁵ = R⁷ = H

2j : R¹ = R⁴ = OH, R², R³ = -OCH₂O-, R⁵ = OMe, R⁶ = R⁷ = H

2k : R¹ = R⁴ = OAc, R², R³ = -OCH₂O-, R⁵ = OMe, R⁶ = R⁷ = H

2l : R¹ = OH, R² = R⁴ = R⁷ = H, R³ = R⁵ = R⁶ = OMe

2m : R¹ = R⁴ = OH, R², R³ = -OCH₂O-, R⁵ = R⁶ = H, R⁷ = OMe

2n : R¹ = R² = R³ = R⁵ = OMe, R⁴ = R⁷ = H, R⁶ = OH

2o : R¹ = R² = R³ = R⁶ = OMe, R⁴ = R⁷ = H, R⁵ = OAc

2p : R¹ = R⁶ = OAc, R² = R⁴ = R⁵ = R⁷ = H, R³ = OMe

2q : R¹ = R³ = R⁶ = OH, R² = R⁴ = R⁵ = R⁷ = H

C-5 positions, respectively, in both 2f and 2g are indicated by the chemical shifts and the splitting patterns of two of their aromatic protons [2f : δ 6.35 and 6.44 (each 1H, d, $J=1.15$ Hz); 2g : δ 6.33 and 6.42 (each 1H, br. s)]. These two aromatic protons of 2f and 2g, thus, correspond to their H-2 and H-6, respectively. Thus, both 2f and 2g contain the same 3-methoxy-4,5-methylene-dioxybenzyl moiety. 2f and 2g, thus, differ from each other in regard to their second benzylic ion-fragments. 2f showed an intense peak at m/z 137 corresponding to the presence of a methoxy and the lone hydroxyl function of

the compound, while the corresponding peak of 2g appearing at m/z 151 which corresponds to the presence of two methoxyl groups. The relative positions of these functional groups in the second benzylic moiety (ring B) of the two compounds were again ascertained by the chemical shifts and the splitting patterns of their remaining three aromatic protons [2f : δ 6.71–6.77 (2H, m) and 6.74 (1H, ill-res., appt. t); 2g : δ 6.74 (1H, d, $J=7.58$ Hz), 6.94 (1H, appt. t, $J_1=7.58$ Hz and $J_2=7.88$ Hz) and 6.79 (1H, d, $J=7.88$ Hz)]. The chemical shifts and the splitting patterns of these three aromatic protons of 2f

Scheme 1. Mass spectral fragmentations of 2f, 2g and 2h.

are strikingly similar to those of the H-4', H-5' and H-6' of cirrhoptalidin (2j)³⁷ possessing a hydroxyl group at C-2' and a methoxy group at C-3'. This would suggest identical substitution pattern, viz. a hydroxyl group at C-2' and a methoxyl function at C-3' also in 2f. This was further supported by the observed downfield shift of H-5' of gastrochilin acetate (2i) by 0.36 ppm (δ 7.10, 1H, apt. t), H-4' and H-6' of 2i appearing at δ 6.75 (1H, ill-res. d, $J=7.8$ Hz) and 6.83 (1H, ill-res. d, $J=7.3$ Hz). By analogy, gastrochilinin (2g) was assumed to contain two of its three aromatic methoxyl groups at C-2' and C-3'. Now coming to amoenylinin (2h), the mass spectrum of the compound showed two intense benzylic ion-frag-

ments at *m/z* 181 (ion-fragment d) and 151 (ion-fragment e). The former containing the phenyl ring A of 2h corresponds to the presence of three methoxyl groups and the latter containing its phenyl ring B indicates the presence of two methoxyl groups. The three methoxyl groups in the phenyl ring A of 2h was placed at C-3, C-4 and C-5 from the chemical shifts and the splitting patterns of two of the five aromatic protons which appeared at δ 6.37 (2H, s) corresponding to two equivalent protons at C-2 and C-6. The remaining two methoxyl groups in the second benzylic moiety of 2h was placed at C-3' and C-4' on the basis of the chemical shifts and the splitting patterns of the remaining three aromatic protons which appeared

at δ 6.66 (1H, d, $J=1.86$ Hz), 6.79 (1H, d, $J=8.1$ Hz) and 6.72 (1H, dd, $J_1=8.1$ Hz and $J_2=1.86$ Hz). These protons were assigned to H-2', H-5' and H-6', respectively. This was also supported by the strikingly similar chemical shifts and the splitting patterns of H-2', H-5' and H-6' of 4'-O-methylgigantol (**2l**)³⁸ [δ 6.66 (1H, d, $J=2.0$ Hz, H-2'), 6.79 (1H, d, $J=8.0$ Hz, H-5') and 6.72 (1H, dd, $J_1=8.0$ Hz and $J_2=2.0$ Hz, H-6')] containing two methoxyl groups at C-3' and C-4' with the three aromatic protons of **2h** of the phenyl ring B.

More compelling evidence in favour of the structures of **2f**, **2g** and **2h** was provided by the ¹³C NMR spectral data of the compounds and in case of **2f** also by those of its acetyl derivative (**2i**) (Table 1). The δ_c values of the compounds not only provided further evidence for the functional groups present in them and the bibenzylic formulation of each compound but also confirmed the relative positions of their functional groups established from their ¹H NMR spectral data. The assignments of the carbon chemical shifts were made by comparison with the δ_c values of structurally similar compounds. Thus, the δ_c values of C- α' , C-1, C-2, C-3, C-4, C-5 and C-6 of gastrochilin (**2f**), gastrochilin acetate (**2i**) and gastrochilinin (**2g**) are virtually identical (Table 1) indicating the presence of the same oxygen substituents in the benzyl unit composed of the above carbon atoms. Again, the striking similarities of the above δ_c values of **2f**, **2i** and **2g** with those of the corresponding carbon atoms of cirrhopedalidin³⁷ (**2j**) and cirrhopedalidin³⁹ (**2m**), each containing a 3-hydroxy-4,5-methylenedioxybenzyl moiety indicate similar oxygen substituents at C-3, C-4 and C-5 in all the compounds. The observed differences in the δ_c values of the aromatic carbon atoms of this benzylic unit of **2f**, **2i** and **2g** from those of the corresponding carbon atoms of **2j** and **2m** are intelligible in terms of the presence of a methoxyl group at C-3 of **2f**, **2i** and **2g** in place of a hydroxyl function at the same position in **2j** and **2m**, C-4 and C-5 of all the compounds being substituted by a methylenedioxy function. The presence of a methylenedioxy group in **2f**, **2i** and **2g** was indicated by the appearance of the characteristic methylene carbon signals at δ_c 100.9, 100.95 and 101.6, respectively, in their ¹³C NMR spectra. Gastrochilin (**2f**), gastrochilin acetate (**2i**) and gastrochilinin (**2g**) are thus composed of a 3-methoxy-4,5-methylenedioxybenzyl moiety.

Now, turning to the second benzylic unit of gastrochilin (**2f**), the virtually identical δ_c values of C- α , C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5' and C-6' of **2f** and cirrhopedalidin (**2j**)

(Table 1) possessing a 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzyl unit affirmed the presence of an identical benzyl moiety also in **2f**. The above contention was also supported by the essentially identical δ_c values of C- α , C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5' and C-6' of gastrochilin acetate (**2i**) and cirrhopedalidin diacetate (**2k**) possessing a 2-acetoxy-3-methoxybenzyl unit. The normal carbon resonances of the methoxy groups of **2f** and **2i** at *ca.* δ_c 55–56 also suggest that the two methoxyl groups in **2f** and **2i** must have at least one *ortho* hydrogen atom. This, in turn, suggests that the methoxyl group in the second benzylic unit of **2f** must be at C-3' rather than at C-2'. The lone hydroxyl group of **2f** must, therefore, be placed at C-2' as in cirrhopedalidin (**2j**). This was further corroborated by the observed downfield shifts of C-1', C-3' and C-5' of **2f** by 7.1, 4.7 and 6.8 ppm, respectively, in the ¹³C NMR spectrum of its acetyl derivative (**2i**). The δ_c values of C- α , C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5' and C-6' of gastrochilinin (**2g**) constituting its second benzylic unit are comparable with those of gastrochilin (**2f**) and cirrhopedalidin (**2j**) (Table 1) suggesting similar oxygenation pattern in ring B of all the three compounds. Since **2g** is devoid of a phenolic hydroxyl group, it appears that it is the 2'-O-methyl ether derivative of **2f**. The δ_c values of the above carbon atoms of **2g** are, in fact, consistent with the above contention. The replacement of the hydroxyl group at C-2' in **2f** by a methoxyl group at the same position in **2g** is indicated by the relatively downfield resonance of one of its methoxyl carbon (δ_c 61.3), the other two methoxyl carbons resonating at the normal region (δ_c 56.1 and 56.9). The absence of the expected upfield shifts of C-1', C-3' and C-5' of **2g** compared with the corresponding carbon atoms of **2f** owing to the replacement of the hydroxyl group of the latter by a methoxyl group in the former may be due to consecutive substitution by two methoxyl groups at C-2' and C-3' and a CH₂ group at C-1'. In such a situation, the methoxyl group at C-2' is pushed out of the plane of the aromatic ring and as a result, the normal additive parameters of the methoxyl group at C-2' are not applicable.

In the case of amoeylinin (**2h**), the virtually identical chemical shifts of C- α' , C-1, C-2, C-3, C-4, C-5 and C-6 of the compound and those of the corresponding carbon atoms of crepidatin (**2n**)⁴⁰ and erianin acetate (**2o**)⁴¹ (Table 1), both possessing a 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzyl unit, affirmed the presence of the same moiety also in **2h**. The appearance of one of the methoxyl carbons at a relatively

Table 1. ^{13}C NMR spectral data of 2f, 2i, 2g, 2j, 2m, 2k, 2h, 2n, 2o and 2c
Chemical shifts (δ_{ppm})*

C	2f	2i	2g	2j	2m	2k	2h	2n	2o	2c
1	136.8	135.9	137.2	137.2	137.5	136.7 ^a	137.3	137.2	139.5	132.8 ^d
2	107.4	107.4	108.0	108.5	111.6	115.2	106.0	108.5	105.4	105.2
3	143.3	143.2	143.8	138.7	141.2	132.7	153.1	138.7	153.0	146.8
4	133.0	133.1	133.2	131.9	133.7	135.9 ^a	134.4	131.9	134.3	133.5 ^d
5	148.5	148.5	149.1	148.5	149.6	149.2	153.1	148.5	153.0	146.8
6	102.4	102.1	102.9	102.2	101.5	106.6	106.0	102.2	105.4	105.2
α	32.1	32.2	32.8	32.0	33.3	32.0	38.3 ^b	32.0	38.8 ^c	38.3 ^e
α'	35.9	36.0	37.6	35.7	36.4	35.8	37.4 ^b	35.7	36.9 ^c	37.3 ^e
1'	127.3	134.4	135.8	127.4	129.7	134.4	132.5	127.4	137.3	132.7 ^d
2'	143.2	137.9	147.6	143.4	149.5	138.0	111.8	143.4	122.4	111.2
3'	146.2	150.9	153.2	146.2	116.4	151.0	143.8	146.2	136.2	146.1
4'	108.4	109.9	110.8	110.5	112.3	110.1	142.2	110.5	149.3	143.7
5'	119.1	125.9	122.4	119.1	153.0	126.2	112.5	119.1	112.3	114.1
6'	122.2	121.5	124.2	122.2	116.0	121.5	120.4	122.2	126.7	121.0
OMe	56.3	56.2	61.3	55.9	55.5	55.8	55.7	55.9	56.0	55.2
	55.8	56.6	56.9	-	-	-	55.9	-	56.1	55.8
	-	-	56.1	-	-	-	56.0	-	-	-
	-	-	-	-	-	-	60.7	-	-	-
	-	-	-	-	-	-	(2 \times OMe)	-	60.9	-
OAc	-	168.7	-	-	-	-	(OMe at C-4)	-	-	-
	-	20.3	-	-	-	-	168.8	-	169.1	-
	-	-	-	-	-	-	168.0	-	-	-
	-	-	-	-	-	-	20.4	-	20.7	-
-OCH ₂ O-	100.9	100.95	101.6	101.1	101.4	101.6	-	-	-	-

*Spectra were run in CDCl_3 and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta_{(\text{TMS})} = \delta_{(\text{CDCl}_3)} + 76.9$ ppm.

^{a-d}Values are interchangeable in each column.

downfield position (δ_{c} 60.7) confirmed the placement of a methoxyl group at C-4 flanked by two methoxyl groups at C-3 and C-5 in **2h**. The carbon atoms of the other methoxyl groups appeared at the normal region (δ_{c} 55–56) indicating the presence of at least one hydrogen atom *ortho* to these methoxyl groups. Again, the carbon resonances of C- α , C-1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5' and C-6' of **2h** are strikingly similar to those of the corresponding carbon atoms moscatilin³⁰ (**2c**) and crepidatin⁴⁰ (**2n**) indicating the presence of a 3,4-dioxygenated benzylic moiety in **2h**, constituting its second benzylic unit. The observed differences in the chemical shifts of the aromatic carbons of **2h** from those of the corresponding carbon atoms of **2c** and **2n** are due to the replacement of the hydroxyl group at C-4' of the latter two compounds by a methoxyl group at the same position in **2h**.

The structures of gastrochilin (**2f**), gastrochilinin (**2g**)

and amoenylinin (**2h**) thus deduced from the foregoing spectral data was finally confirmed by the following chemical correlations. Thus, methylation of moscatilin (**2c**) with CH_2N_2 afforded amoenylinin (**2h**) (Scheme 2) confirming the structure of the latter to be 4,4'-O-dimethyl ether of **2c**. Similar treatment of gastrochilin (**2f**) with CH_2N_2 yielded gastrochilinin (**2g**) (Scheme 2) which is thus 2'-O-methyl ether of **2f**.

Gastrochilin (**2f**), gastrochilinin (**2g**) and amoenylinin (**2h**) are thus three new additions to the growing list of the naturally occurring bibenzyl derivatives. In view of the fact that several bibenzyl derivatives are reported to exhibit pronounced antimutagenic property⁴², while others are known to act as potent endogenous plant growth regulators⁴³, it would be interesting to study the above bibenzyl derivatives for similar biological activities.

Scheme 2. Chemical conversion of 2f to 2g and 2c to 2h.

The structure of 2e which was first detected by TLC and GLC of the extract of *Cannabis sativa* was established as 3,4'-dihydroxy-5-methoxybibenzyl mainly from its ¹H NMR and mass spectral data and later by two independent synthesis^{32a,b}. We have carried out the following additional spectral studies of the compound and its diacetyl derivative with a view to further confirming its proposed structure. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the diacetyl derivative 2p of 2e showed signals at δ 2.28 (6H, s; 2 × OAc), 2.88 (4H, s; H₂-α and H₂-α'), 3.75 (3H, s; Ar-OMe), 6.41, 6.45 and 6.50 (each 1H, ill-res., m-coupled apt. t; H-2, H-4 and H-6), 6.99 (2H, d, J=9.0 Hz, H-3' and H-5') and 7.16 (2H, d, J=9.0 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), which are also in conformity with the structure 2p for the diacetate and hence 2e for the parent phenol. The structure 2e for the parent compound has now been further confirmed by its ¹³C NMR spectral data (Table 2). The degree of protonation of each carbon atom was determined by DEPT experiment and the assignments of the carbon chemical shifts were made by comparison with the δ_c values of structurally similar compounds, viz. batatasin-III (2d)³¹ and dihydroresveratrol (2q)⁴⁴. Thus, the carbon resonances at δ_c 38.1 (or 36.6), 145.2, 108.0, 159.5, 98.9, 161.4, 106.7 and 55.2 are essentially identical with those of C-α', C-1, C-2, C-3, C-4, C-5, C-6 and OMe of batatasin-III (2d), respectively (Table 2), confirming the presence of a 3-hydroxy-5-methoxybenzyl moiety also in compound 2e. Again, the signals at δ_c 36.6 (or 38.1), 133.8, 129.4, 115.1, 154.2, 115.1 and 129.4 of 2e are virtually identical with those of C-α, C-

1', C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5' and C-6', respectively, of dihydroresveratrol (2q) (Table 2) affirming the presence of a 4-hydroxybenzyl unit also in 2e as the second benzylic unit of its bibenzyl formulation. The structure of 2e is thus firmly established as 3,4'-dihydroxy-5-methoxybibenzyl as proposed earlier.

Both amotin (4)³⁵ and amoenin (5)³⁶ were also isolated earlier from *D. amoenum*, although direct comparison with the authentic compounds could not be made possible due to unavailability of authentic samples. The structures of amotin (4) and amoenin (5) were established from their various spectral data and confirmed by chemical correlation with compounds of known structures and stereochemistry. Thus, the formation of 4 from aduncin (6)³⁶ (Scheme 3) isolated from *D. aduncum* and the transformation of amoenin (5) to α-dihydrocicrotoxin (7)⁴⁵ (Scheme 4) of known absolute stereochemistry firmly established their assigned structures and stereochemistry. But the ¹H NMR of amotin earlier recorded in d₅-pyridine exhibited very poor resolution of the signals and barring only three protons at C-2, C-3 and C-5 other proton resonances were not specifically assigned. The carbon resonances of amotin (also recorded in d₅-pyridine) also were not specifically assigned.

We have carried out an extensive ¹H, ¹³C and 2D NMR (COSY, HMQC and HMBC) spectral studies on amotin. Thus, the 500 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum of amotin in d₆-acetone exhibited well separated signals for all the 20 protons of the compound (including the two hydroxyl protons) with excellent resolutions. With the help of

Table 2. ^{13}C NMR spectral data of 2e, 2d, 2q and 4
Chemical shifts (δ_{ppm})

C	2e [†]	2d [†]	2q [†]	C	4 ^{††}
1	145.2	145.0 ^b	145.0	1	50.5
2	108.0	108.8	107.7	2	83.2
3	159.5	159.2	157.9	3	83.6
4	98.9	99.9	100.7	4	81.8
5	161.4	161.9	157.9	5	51.8
6	106.7	106.3	107.7	6	47.4
α	38.1 ^a	38.4 ^c	38.8 ^d	7	30.1
α'	36.6 ^a	38.1 ^c	37.3 ^d	8	37.8
1'	133.8	144.3 ^b	133.2	9	85.6
2'	129.4	116.2	129.9	10	25.3
3'	115.1	158.2	115.8	11	177.0
4'	154.2	113.6	154.8	12	28.8
5'	115.1	130.5	115.8	13	16.4 ^e
6'	129.4	120.4	129.9	14	15.8 ^e
OMe	55.2	55.3	-	15	177.7

[†]Spectra were run in CDCl_3 and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta_{(\text{TMS})} = \delta_{(\text{CDCl}_3)} + 76.9$ ppm; ^{††}Spectra were run in d_6 -acetone at 125 MHz and the chemical shifts were measured with $\delta_{(\text{TMS})} = \delta_{(d_6\text{-acetone})} + 29.6$ ppm.

^{a-e}Values are interchangeable in each column.

COSY, HMQC and HMBC spectral analysis all the proton resonances of amotin were unambiguously assigned [δ 4.86 (s; OH at C-9), 4.53 (s; OH at C-4), 4.48 (dd, $J_1=3.5$ Hz and $J_2=0.96$ Hz, H-3), 4.32 (d, $J=3.5$ Hz, H-2), 2.39 (dd, $J_1=6.26$ Hz and $J_2=0.96$ Hz, H-5), 2.23 (8 lines m, H-6), 2.16 (13 lines m, $\text{H}_{\beta-7}$), 2.06 (7 lines m, $\text{H}_{\beta-8}$), 1.92 (11 lines m, H-12), 1.79 (dd, $J_1=12.6$

Hz and $J_2=6.37$ Hz, $\text{H}_{\alpha-7}$), 1.65 (ddd, $J_1=14.1$ Hz, $J_2=6.41$ Hz and $J_3=1.04$ Hz, $\text{H}_{\alpha-8}$), 1.28 (s, H_3 -10), 0.91 (d, $J=6.75$ Hz, H_3 -13 or H_3 -14) and 0.88 (d, $J=6.69$ Hz, H_3 -14 or H_3 -13)]. The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the compound run at 125 MHz also in d_6 -acetone exhibited signals for all the 15 carbon atoms of the compound and the degree of protonation of each carbon atom was ascertained by DEPT experiments and those of the protonated carbon atoms were confirmed by the 1-bond ^1H - ^{13}C correlations (HMQC). Unambiguous assignments of all the carbon resonances of amotin (4) (Table 2) were made by the ^1H - ^{13}C correlations exhibited by the HMQC and HMBC spectra of the compound.

The COSY spectrum of 4 showed the following ^1H - ^1H correlations: (i) Strong 3-bond correlations between the protons at δ 0.88 (H_3 -13 or H_3 -14) and 0.91 (H_3 -14 or H_3 -13) and the proton at δ 1.92 (H-12); (ii) a strong 2-bond correlation between the proton at δ 1.65 (assigned to $\text{H}_{\alpha-8}$) and that at δ 2.06 (attributed to $\text{H}_{\beta-8}$) [due to geminal coupling]; (iii) a fairly strong 3-bond correlation between the protons at δ 1.65 ($\text{H}_{\alpha-8}$) and 2.16 ($\text{H}_{\beta-7}$); (iv) strong 3-bond correlation between the proton at δ 1.79 (assigned to $\text{H}_{\alpha-7}$) and the proton at δ 2.06 ($\text{H}_{\beta-8}$) and a strong 2-bond correlation between the same proton and the proton at δ 2.16 ($\text{H}_{\beta-7}$) [The relatively lowfield resonances of $\text{H}_{\beta-8}$ (δ 2.06) and $\text{H}_{\beta-7}$ (δ 2.16) compared with $\text{H}_{\alpha-8}$ (δ 1.65) and $\text{H}_{\alpha-7}$ (δ 1.79) was attributed to the proximity of $\text{H}_{\beta-7}$ and $\text{H}_{\beta-8}$ to the deshielding zone of the β -oriented lactone carbonyl at C-15]; (v) a fairly strong 3-bond correlation between the proton at δ 2.06 ($\text{H}_{\beta-8}$) and that at δ 2.16 ($\text{H}_{\beta-7}$); (vi) strong 3-bond corre-

Scheme 3. Conversion of 6 (aduncin) to 4 (amotin).

Scheme 4. Chemical conversion of 5 (amoenin) to 7 (α-dihydropicrotoxin).

lations between the proton at δ 2.23 (H-6) and those at δ 2.39 (H-5) and 2.16 (H_p-7); (vii) a fairly strong 4-bond correlation between the proton at δ 2.39 (H-5) and that at δ 2.16 (H_p-7); (viii) strong 3-bond correlation between the proton at δ 4.32 (assigned to H-2 by HMQC and HMBC) and that at δ 4.48 (H-3); (ix) the methyl singlet at δ 1.28 and the hydroxyl proton signals at δ 4.53 and 4.86, however, as expected, showed no correlation with any proton of the compound. The ¹H-¹H correlations exhibited by the COSY spectrum of amotin (4) showing the relative positions of its protons and affirming their assignments are shown in its structural diagram (Fig. 1).

The HMBC spectrum of amotin (4) [recorded with J_{C-H} parameter set to 7 Hz] is unique in displaying maxi-

um ¹H-¹³C correlations (mostly 3-bond and 2-bond), which coupled with its HMQC spectrum (recorded with J_{C-H} parameter set to 160 Hz) has provided the most convincing evidence for the assignments of all the carbon and proton chemical shifts of the compound. These correlations are summarized below.

(i) The two hydroxyl proton resonances at δ 4.86 (s) and 4.53 (s) of 4 are readily identifiable. They correspond to the protons of the hydroxyl groups at C-9 and C-4. But which of them corresponds to which hydroxyl proton were to be ascertained. This was made possible by their correlations (3-bond and 2-bond) with the carbon atoms of the compound exhibited by its HMBC spectrum. Thus, the proton resonance at δ 4.86 showed strong

Fig. 1. The ¹H-¹H correlations exhibited by the COSY spectrum of amotin (4).

2-bond correlation with the nonprotonated carbon at δ_c 85.6. The above proton also showed strong 3-bond correlations with the methylene carbon at δ_c 37.8 and the nonprotonated carbons at δ_c 50.5 and 177.0, the latter being assignable only to one of the lactone carbonyl carbons. The carbon resonance at δ_c 37.8 corresponds to one of the two methylene carbons of 4 as evident from the HMQC spectrum of the compound showing 1-bond correlations with both the proton resonances at δ 2.06 and 1.65. The 3-bond correlation of the hydroxyl proton resonance at δ 4.86 with the carbon resonance at δ_c 37.8 thus implies that the carbon signal at δ_c 37.8 must be assigned to C-8 and the proton signal at δ 4.86 to the proton of the hydroxyl group at C-9. This, in turn, also affirms that the nonprotonated carbon resonances at δ_c 85.6, 50.5 and 177.0 correspond to C-9, C-1 and C-11, respectively. Again, since the carbon resonance at δ_c 37.8 (C-8) showed 1-bond correlations with the proton resonances at δ 2.06 and 1.65 (HMQC), these signals must also correspond to H $_{\beta}$ -8 and H $_{\alpha}$ -8, respectively. The other hydroxyl proton resonance at δ 4.53 which must then be assigned to the proton of the hydroxyl group at C-4 showed strong 2-bond correlation with the carbon resonance at δ_c 81.8 and strong 3-bond correlations with the methine carbon resonances at δ_c 83.6 and 51.8, which showed 1-bond correlations (HMQC) with the proton resonances at δ 4.48 and 2.39, respectively. This would, therefore, suggest that the carbon resonances at δ_c 81.8, 83.6 and 51.8 must be assigned to C-4, C-3 and C-5, respectively, and the methine proton signals at δ 4.48 and 2.39 must be assigned to H-3 and H-5, respectively.

(ii) The proton resonance at δ 4.48 (already assigned to H-3) exhibited strong 3-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 50.5 and 177.7. The former has already been assigned to C-1. The latter may, therefore, be attributed to the second lactone carbonyl carbon (C-15). The above proton signal at δ 4.48 also showed strong 2-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 81.8 (already assigned to C-4) and 83.2. The latter thus corresponds to the second lactone methine carbon (C-2).

(iii) The proton at δ 4.32 (H-2) showed strong 2-bond correlations with the carbon signals at δ_c 50.5 and 83.6 (already assigned to C-1 and C-3, respectively) and strong 3-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 85.6, 177.0, 25.3 and 47.4, of which the signals at δ_c 85.6 and 177.0 have already been assigned to C-9 and C-11, respectively. The carbon resonances at δ_c 25.3 and 47.4, which showed 1-bond correlations (HMQC) with the proton signals at δ 1.28 (methyl protons) and 2.23 (methine

proton). The carbon resonances at δ_c 25.3 and 47.4 may, therefore, be assigned to C-10 and C-6, respectively, and accordingly, the proton signals at δ 1.28 and 2.23 may be attributed to H $_3$ -10 and H-6, respectively.

(iv) The proton at δ 2.06 attributed to H $_{\beta}$ -8 exhibited a strong 3-bond correlation with the carbon resonance at δ_c 177.0 (already assigned to C-11) and a fairly strong 2-bond correlation with the carbon signal at δ_c 30.1, which showed 1-bond correlations (HMQC) with the proton resonances at δ 2.16 and 1.79. The above proton signals may, therefore, be attributed to H $_{\beta}$ -7 and H $_{\alpha}$ -7, respectively. The carbon resonance at δ_c 30.1 thus corresponds to the second methylene carbon (C-7) of 4. The proton at δ 2.06 also exhibited a weak 6-bond correlation with the carbon at δ_c 28.8 (assigned to C-12).

(v) Similarly, the proton at δ 1.65 (already assigned to H $_{\alpha}$ -8) exhibited strong 2-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 30.1 and 85.6, which have already been assigned to C-7 and C-9, respectively. The above proton also showed fairly strong 3-bond correlations with the carbon signals at δ_c 50.5 and 47.4, which have also been assigned to C-1 and C-6, respectively.

(vi) The proton at δ 2.16 (assigned to H $_{\beta}$ -7) displayed strong 2-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 37.8 and 47.4, which have already been assigned to C-8 and C-6, respectively.

(vii) Similarly, the proton at δ 1.79 exhibited strong 2-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 37.8 (C-8) and 47.4 (C-6) and strong 3-bond correlations with the carbon signals at δ_c 50.5 (C-1) and 85.6 (C-9). The above proton signal also showed a weak 5-bond correlation with the carbon resonance at δ_c 28.8 which has already been assigned to C-12.

(viii) The proton signal at δ 2.23 (H-6) showed strong 3-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 37.8, 85.6, 25.3 and 177.7, which have already been assigned to C-8, C-9, C-10 and C-15, respectively. The above proton signal also exhibited a strong 2-bond correlation with the carbon resonance at δ_c 50.5 (assigned to C-1).

(ix) The proton signal at δ 2.39 (assigned to H-5) exhibited strong 2-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 81.8, 47.4 and 177.7, which have already been assigned to C-4, C-6 and C-15, respectively. The above proton signal also showed strong 3-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 50.5 and 83.6, which have also been already assigned to C-1 and C-3, respectively.

(x) The proton resonance at δ 1.92 (assigned to C-12) showed strong 2-bond correlations with the methyl carbon signals at δ_c 15.8 and 16.4, which may be assigned to C-14 and C-13. The above proton signal also showed a weak 5-bond correlation with the carbon resonance at δ_c 30.1 (C-6) and a similar weak 6-bond correlation with the carbon resonance at δ_c 37.8 (C-8).

(xi) The proton signal at δ 1.28 (H_3 -10) showed strong 3-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 85.6, 83.2 and 47.4, which have already been assigned to C-9, C-2 and C-6, respectively. The above proton signal also exhibited a strong 2-bond correlation with the carbon resonance at δ_c 50.5 (C-1).

(xii) Both the methyl proton signals at δ 0.88 (H_3 -13

or H_3 -14) and 0.91 (H_3 -14 or H_3 -13) exhibited strong 3-bond correlation with the carbon resonance at δ_c 81.8 (already assigned to C-4). The above proton signal also showed a strong 2-bond correlation with the carbon resonance at δ_c 28.8 (already assigned to C-12).

The above 1H - ^{13}C correlations exhibited by the HMBC spectrum of amotin (4) are shown on its structural diagram (Fig. 2).

The above NMR spectral studies carried out on amotin thus further confirmed its assigned structure 4. The 2D NMR spectral (COSY, HMQC and HMBC) correlation studies, in particular, described above have provided the most convincing evidence for unambiguous assignments of all the proton and carbon resonances of amotin (4).

Fig. 2. The long range (mostly 3- and 2-bond) 1H - ^{13}C correlations exhibited by the HMBC spectrum of amotin (4).

The results of the above 2D NMR spectral studies thus demonstrate a unique example of the power of this spectroscopic technique in the structural elucidation of complex natural products and have provided valuable information which would be extremely useful for characterization of other compounds structurally related to amotin (4).

Experimental

M.p.s : uncorr. CC : silica gel (100–200 mesh). MPLC : silica gel (200–300 mesh). TLC : silica gel-G. IR : KBr discs. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR : 300 Mz and 500 Mz (^1H) and 75 Mz and 125 Mz (^{13}C). NMR spectra were recorded in d_6 -acetone (4 and 2g), d_5 -pyridine (5) and CDCl_3 (remaining compounds) using TMS as internal standard. Chemical shifts were expressed in δ_{ppm} . The carbon chemical shifts were measured in ppm downfield from TMS : $\delta_{(\text{TMS})} = \delta_{(\text{CDCl}_3)} + 76.9$ ppm and $\delta_{(\text{TMS})} = \delta_{(d_6\text{-acetone})} + 29.6$ ppm. HMQC and HMBC spectra of 4 were recorded in d_6 -acetone in a 500 MHz instrument with $J_{\text{C-H}}$ parameters set to 160 Hz and 7 Hz, respectively. MS : direct inlet system, 70 eV. All analyt. samples were routinely dried over P_2O_5 for 24 h *in vacuo* and were tested for purity by TLC and MS. The petrol used had b.p. 60–80 °C. Anhydrous Na_2SO_4 was used for drying organic solvents.

Plant materials :

Gastrochilum calcoelaria D. Don and *Dendrobium amoenum* Wall were collected from Kalimpong (Darjeeling, India) in August, 2002. The voucher specimens of the two orchids (Majumder s.n.) were deposited in the Herbarium of the Department of Botany, University of Calcutta (CUH).

Isolation of gastrochilin (2f), gastrochilinin (2g), amoenylinin (2h), 1a, 1b, 2a, 2b, 2c, 2d, 2e, 3a, 3b, 4, 5, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and β -sitosterol :

Air-dried finely powdered whole plants of *G. calcoelaria* and *D. amoenum* (each 2 kg) were separately kept soaked in MeOH for three weeks at room temperature. The MeOH extracts were then drained out and concentrated under reduced pressure to ca. 100 ml. The concentrated extract in each case was diluted with H_2O (500 ml) and exhaustively extracted with Et_2O . The Et_2O extract in each case was fractionated into acidic and nonacidic fractions using 2 M NaOH solution. The aqueous alkaline solution in each case was then acidified in the cold with conc. HCl and the liberated solids were extracted with

Et_2O , washed with H_2O , dried and the solvent was removed. The Et_2O extract containing the nonacidic constituents (left after treatment with 2 M NaOH) in each case was washed with H_2O , dried and the solvent removed. The residues containing the acidic and nonacidic (neutral) compounds in each case were separately chromatographed.

Chromatography of the acidic fraction obtained from *G. calcoelaria* :

The early fractions of the petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate afforded gastrochilin (2f) (0.05 g), crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 60 °C (Found : C, 67.47; H, 6.11. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 67.54; H, 5.96%); UV λ_{max} nm : 211.5 and 277.5 (log ϵ 4.21 and 3.06); UV λ_{max} nm (0.1 M NaOH-EtOH) : 215.0 and 281.5 (log ϵ 4.27 and 3.14); IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 3400 (OH), 1630, 1510, 890, 830, 815, 800, 775 (aromatic nucleus); MS m/z (rel. int.) : 302 [M^+] (15), 166 (97), 165 (100), 181 (10.1), 137 (85.7), 136 (14), 122 (16), 120 (60), 94 (43), 92 (55), 79 (51), 77 (76) and 64 (46). Gastrochilin (2f) was acetylated with Ac_2O and pyridine in the usual manner to give gastrochilin acetate (2i) as a semisolid mass (Found : C, 66.20; H, 5.87. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6$ requires : C, 66.27; H, 5.81%); UV λ_{max} nm : 215, 263.5 and 281.5 (log ϵ 4.27, 2.93 and 3.14); IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 1220 and 1750 (OAc), 1630, 1510, 845, 830, 825, 810 and 780 (aromatic nucleus); MS m/z (rel. int.) : 344 [M^+] (12), 302 (13.5), 188 (98), 165 (100), 151 (10) and 137 (84).

Further elution of the main column with petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) gave a mixture of 1a and 1b. Rechromatography of this mixture with the same solvent afforded, in the early fractions, 1a (0.05 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 185 °C and 1b, in the later fractions, also crystallized from the same solvent, m.p. 135 °C. 1a and 1b were identified with confusarin and 2,7-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene, respectively, by direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p. and TLC) with their respective authentic samples.

Chromatography of the neutral fraction obtained from *G. calcoelaria* :

The petrol-EtOAc (90 : 1) eluate afforded gastrochilinin (2g) (0.07 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 56 °C (Found : C, 68.23; H, 6.40. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 68.35; H, 6.32%). UV λ_{max} nm : 221.0 and 276.5 (log ϵ 4.16 and 3.36); IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 1631, 1505, 1475, 840, 816 and 785 (aromatic nucleus); MS m/z (rel. int.) : 316 [M^+] (58), 166 (30.1), 165 (100), 151 (24.7), 136 (24.7),

120 (8.6), 91 (23) and 77 (17.2).

Chromatography of the acidic fraction obtained from D. amoenum :

The petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) eluate gave **2b** (0.02 g) as a semisolid mass. It was identified with isoamoenylin by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Further elution of the main column with petrol-EtOAc (30 : 1) gave a mixture of **2a**, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and **2e**. The above mixture was rechromatographed. The early fractions of the petrol-EtOAc (30 : 1) eluate gave *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.03 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 115 °C, identified by direct comparison with an authentic sample. The later fractions of the same eluate afforded a mixture of **2a** and **2e**. Repeated MPLC of the above mixture using petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) as the solvent system finally gave, in the early fractions, pure **2a** (0.09 g) as a semisolid mass and **2e** (0.08 g), in the later fractions, crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 112 °C. **2a** and **2e** were identified with amoenylin and 3,4'-dihydroxy-5-methoxybibenzyl, respectively, by direct comparison with their respective authentic samples.

Washing the main column with petrol-EtOAc (15 : 1) afforded pure **2c** (0.05 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 84 °C. Elution of the main column with petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) gave a mixture of **2d** and **3b**. Repeated chromatography of this mixture gave, in the early fractions of the petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1), pure **2d** (0.1 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 98 °C. The later fractions of the same eluate afforded pure **3b** (0.015 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 200 °C. **2c**, **2d** and **3b** were identified with moscatilin, batatasin-III and flaccidin, respectively by direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p. and TLC) with their respective authentic samples.

Elution of the main column with petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) gave mixture of **3a**, **4** and **5**. Further chromatography of this mixture using the same solvent system finally gave pure **3a** (0.1 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 145 °C. It was identified with imbricatin by direct comparison with an authentic sample. The later fractions of the above eluate gave a mixture of **4** and **5**. Repeated MPLC of this mixture using petrol-EtOAc (1 : 1) as the solvent system finally gave pure **4** (0.08 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc mixture, m.p. 256 °C and **5** (0.02 g), also crystallized from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 198 °C. **4** and **5** were identified as amotin and amoenin, respectively, by independent spectral measurements. Amotin (**4**) : IR ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 3100–3600 (OH), 1785 and 1765 (γ -lactone carbonyl); MS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 296 [M^+] (0.8), 253 (0.8), 234 (1), 226 (1), 219 (5), 209 (12), 206

(6), 191 (42), 179 (10), 173 (15), 163 (21), 147 (82), 137 (19), 133 (18), 119 (28), 97 (39), 93 (28), 71 (26), 55 (29), 43 (100) and 41 (60). Amoenin (**5**) : IR ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 3065–3655 and 3055 (OH), 1778 and 1752 (γ -lactone carbonyl); 300 MHz ^1H NMR (in d_5 -pyridine) : δ 6.75 (3H, d, $J=6.6$ Hz), 1.05 (3H, d, $J=6.2$ Hz), 1.07 (3H, s), 2.07–2.28 (11H, m), 2.35 (1H, d, $J=14$ Hz), 2.45–2.83 (1H, m), 2.76 (1H, dd, $J_1=14$ Hz, $J_2=3.5$ Hz), 2.86 (1H, d, $J=3.5$ Hz), 3.71 (1H, d, $J=3.5$ Hz), 4.14 (1H, d, $J=13$ Hz), 4.51 (1H, s), 4.97 (1H, d, $J=5.5$ Hz), 5.05 (s, OH; disappeared on deuterium exchange) and 5.16 (1H, d, $J=13$ Hz); MS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 298 [M^+] (2), 282 (1), 280 (2), 267 (3), 262 (6), 255 (2), 249 (3), 237 (11), 222 (10), 209 (16), 191 (27), 166 (43), 151 (24), 143 (77), 125 (79), 109 (49), 97 (96), 43 (96) and 41 (100).

Chromatography of the neutral fraction obtained from D. amoenum :

The petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) eluate afforded **2h** (0.03 g) as a semisolid mass (Found : C, 68.64; H, 7.20. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 68.67; H, 7.23%). UV λ_{\max} nm 210.5 and 277.5 ($\log \epsilon$ 4.23 and 3.20); IR ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 1590, 1511, 1459, 812 and 766 (aromatic nucleus); MS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 332 [M^+] (49), 181 (100), 165 (5), 151 (100) and 136 (7).

Further washing the column with petrol-EtOAc (50 : 1) gave β -sitosterol, crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 136 °C, identified by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

Conversion of gastrochilin (2f) to gastrochilinin (2g) and moscatilin (2c) to amoenylinin (2h) :

Gastrochilin (**2f**) (0.03 g) dissolved in MeOH (20 ml) was treated with a solution of 4 molar equivalent of CH_2N_2 in Et_2O (20 ml) and the mixture was kept overnight in an ice-bath. Removal of solvent gave a residue which was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (90 : 1) eluate gave pure **2g** (0.025 g), crystallized from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 56 °C.

To a solution of moscatilin (**2c**) (0.02 g) in MeOH (10 ml) was added excess of CH_2N_2 in Et_2O and the solution was kept overnight in an ice-bath. Removal of solvent left a residue which was chromatographed. The petrol-EtOAc (80 : 1) gave **2h** (0.015 g) as a semisolid mass.

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